

MATERIAL USED: PERSONAL FACTORS QUESTIONNAIRE

Part 1: Personal Characteristics

- What is your age?
- What is your gender? (Female/ Male/ Other/ No answer | prefer not to say)
- What region are you from? (North America/ Asia & Pacific/ Europe/ South/Latin America/ Africa)
- What's your mother language? (German/ Spanish/ English/ Other)
- What is the highest degree or level of education you have completed? (Undergraduate program/ Postgraduate program (PhD)/ Postgraduate program (Master)/ Postgraduate program (Postdoctoral))
- What is your current activity? (Studying/ Working/ Studying and working and/ No activity.)

Part 2: Business Process Model

- Check your previous experience with business process models (I have never heard of it / I have heard of it / I have received class(es) about it / I have occasionally worked with it / I use it routinely in my work)
- How do you assess your theoretical knowledge on business process modeling? (I have weak theoretical knowledge / I have rather weak theoretical knowledge / I have mediocre theoretical knowledge / I have rather strong theoretical knowledge / I have strong theoretical knowledge)
- How often do you use business process modeling in practice? (I never use business process modeling in practice / I sometimes use business process modeling in practice / I regularly use business process modeling in practice, but not every day / I use business process modeling in practice every day)